

THE PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO
THE STUDY OF THE TRIAD -N·C·S-. PART X. ACTION
OF HYDROLYTIC AGENTS, ALKALINE LEAD
ACETATE, AND NITROUS ACID ON
THIOSEMICARBAZIDE.

BY RAMCHANDRA SAHASRABUDHEY AND HANS KRALL.

Thiosemicarbazide on refluxing with *N*-alkali decomposes to $\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{NHCN}$ and H_2S , and with *N*-HCl very little change takes place, only small amount of it decomposes to $\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{NH}_2$ and HCNS . Alkaline lead acetate has been found to desulphurise thiosemicarbazide; from the desulphurised product a picrate of probable composition $(\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{NHCN})_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_3\cdot\text{OH}$ has been isolated. Nitrous acid has been found to transform thiosemicarbazide into amidothiotriazole.

By analogy with phenylthiocarbamide (Mehta and Krall, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 635) the decomposition of thiosemicarbazide is expected to proceed according to the following equations :

All these products have been found excepting thiocyanamide, which undergoes further decomposition (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2500); aminocyanamide could be detected only in traces in the form of a picrate, perhaps of its dipolymer.

Refluxing with *N*-alkali in molecular proportions gave :

Time 1 hour. Found : HCNS , 1'44%, NH_3 , 0'48%, H_2S , 7'8%.

Time 4 hours. Found : HCNS , 10'5%, NH_3 , 10'2%, H_2S , 21'6%.

From these figures it is evident that the decomposition takes place predominantly according to the equation (i). The excessive formation of ammonia, with comparatively little hydrogen sulphide on prolonged heating indicates the further hydrolysis of aminocyanamide. With *N*-hydrochloric acid very little change occurs, but equation (ii) predominates. The trend of these changes, both with alkalis and acids, is similar to those with phenylthiocarbamide. The following schematic representation indicates the prototropic change involved in the tautomerism of thiosemicarbazide.

In acid medium :

In basic medium :

An acid medium favours the change to the pseudo form.

Action of Alkaline Lead Acetate.—Alkaline lead acetate is found to desulphurise thiosemicarbazide. Aminocyanamide is expected to be formed:

From the desulphurised product a picrate (m.p. 272°) is obtained which gives nitrogen values agreeing with the composition

Action of Nitrous Acid.—Freund and Schander (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2500) found that thiosemicarbazide reacted in equimolecular proportions with nitrous acid at ordinary temperatures forming amidothiotriazole.

A gasometric study of this reaction has been undertaken and it is found that practically no gas is evolved in presence of normal hydrochloric acid. Amidothiotriazole has been isolated from this mixture confirming that the reaction can be represented as

(Amidothiotriazole.)

A second equivalent of nitrous acid in presence of *N*-hydrochloric acid produces 19.2 c.c. of the gas at N. T. P. from $\frac{1}{2}$ mg. mole of thiosemicarbazide. The composition of the gas is found to be 20% NO and 80% N₂. Evidently this is only the action of nitrous acid on the amidothiotriazole first produced, indicating that it too is tautomeric and may be worth investigating.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Thiosemicarbazide was prepared by isomerising hydrazine thiocyanate (*cf. Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2501). By careful manipulation the yield was increased by about 15%, for it was found that if heating was continued after the mixture had begun to froth, signs of decomposition appeared and the yield decreased. Thiosemicarbazide with ferric salts is found to give a red colouration which is not extractible with ether.

Estimation of Thiocyanic Acid.—The hydrolysate obtained is a complicated mixture containing unchanged thiosemicarbazide with hydrogen sulphide, and thiocyanic acid in the form of their alkali salts, and hydrazine and aminocyanamide etc. The facts that (i) many of these are of a strong reducing nature; (ii) thiosemicarbazide itself gives a red colouration with ferric salts in presence of nitric acid; (iii) it also reacts under the same conditions with silver nitrate; (iv) hydrogen sulphide persists even in presence of dilute nitric acid render the estimation of thiocyanic acid difficult. The procedure finally adopted was to neutralise the alkaline solution with slight excess of dilute sulphuric acid. This removed some of the hydrogen sulphide and the remainder was removed by precipitation with freshly prepared cadmium carbonate. The filtrate was treated with dilute sulphuric acid and warmed; *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde in hot aqueous solution was then added drop by drop with constant stirring, the mixture being maintained just below the boiling point for about 5 minutes. The liquid was cooled to room temperature and filtered, thiocyanic acid being estimated in the filtrate by Volhard's method.

Estimation of Hydrogen Sulphide.—The mixture, taken in a wide test tube fitted with a cork with two delivery tubes, was decomposed with 6 *N*-sulphuric acid and a steady stream of carbon dioxide bubbled through it for 1 hour. The hydrogen sulphide was thus swept on to a zinc acetate trap containing approximately *N*/₅-zinc acetate solution to which were added ammonium chloride and ammonium acetate, where it was precipitated as zinc sulphide. The precipitate, filtered and washed with a little water containing ammonium chloride and ammonium acetate, was added to an excess of standard iodine solution and decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid, the excess of iodine being titrated with thiosulphate.

The apparatus was completely air-tight to avoid oxidation of hydrogen sulphide.

C O N C L U S I O N S.

1. As with phenylthiocarbamide (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 636) the hydrolysis of thiosemicarbazide either with acids or alkalis is of a dissociation type rather than truly hydrolytic.

2. Change No. (i) predominates in alkaline medium, while (ii) is more marked in acidic or neutral media. There is no conclusive evidence of change (iii), and if it takes place at all, it goes to a very small extent. These changes indicate that thiosemicarbazide exists predominantly in the carbamide structure $(\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \overset{\text{H}}{\underset{\text{S}}{\text{C}}} \cdot \text{NH}_2)$ in alkaline medium, while in acid or

neutral media the predominant form is $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \overset{\text{H}}{\underset{\text{SH}}{\text{C}}} = \text{NH}$.

3. Thiosemicarbazide is more reluctant to undergo dissociation; the extent of its decompositions is less than those of phenylthiocarbamide.

4. Thiosemicarbazide like phenylthiocarbamide undergoes desulphurisation with alkaline lead acetate. No aminocyanamide was isolated, but a picrate with the probable composition $(\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CN})_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot (\text{NO}_2)_3 \cdot \text{OH}$ was obtained, m.p. 272° .

5. Nitrous acid in 1 : 1 ratio transforms thiosemicarbazide into amidohiotriazole. In 2 : 1 ratio gases are formed, but this is evidence of tautomerism in the amidohiotriazole first formed.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE AGRA.

Received January 13, 1941.